

The Implementation of Pancasila Values to Early Children Through Traditional Ceremonies in Banceuy Community

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Abstract:

This study aims to find a model for inculcating Pancasila values to early childhood through traditional ceremonies in Banceuy Village, Subang, West Java. This research is a type of descriptive research with a qualitative approach. To obtain data, in-depth observations and interviews were conducted. In order to obtain accurate data, four validation steps were carried out using; member check, audit trial, triangulation, and theoretical expert opinion. This study discusses (1) whether in traditional ceremonies there are Pancasila values that are in accordance with the needs of early childhood, (2) what Pancasila values are instilled in early childhood through the Ngaruwat Bumi

Traditional Ceremony and Nyapu Overtime, (3) how to instill Pancasila values into early childhood through the Ngaruwat Bumi and Nyapu Overtime ceremonies that occurred in the Banceuy Traditional Village. This study concludes that the values of Pancasila that are instilled in early childhood through the Ruwatan Bumi and Nyapu Overtime ceremonies in the Banceuy Traditional Village, Subang, West Java, are Divine Values, Human Values, Unity Values, Deliberation and Representative Values, and Social Justice Values. Value planting activities carried out through traditional ceremonies are (a) Ritual Activities in the form of Hajat Mawar. Maulud Aki Leutik, Hajat Solokan, (b) Art activities include Rengkong, Tuunggulan, and Kolecer, as well as cikibung, jibrut, and miruha games, in front of early childhood children, so that early childhood can follow the values instilled through these activities. (c) Meanwhile, the traditional Nyapu Overtime ceremony is carried out to maintain the cleanliness of the village, environment, and yard of the Banceuy Traditional Village residents.

Keywords: *Traditional Ceremony, Early Childhood, Banceuy Traditional Village, Pancasila Values.*

Introduction

By referring to the Main Performance Index (KPI) of the Ministry of Education and Culture

in 2020, part five (5), which is to increase the number of research and community service outputs that have succeeded in getting international recognition or applied by the

community per number of lecturers (Baring, et al., 2021; Rahmadi, Hayati, & Nursyifa, 2020). The IKU encourages and provides opportunities for Jakarta State University (UNJ) to design and simultaneously develop the Leading Research Fields for 2021 – 2025. The Leading Research Fields for 2021 – 2025, number three (3) are Social Humanities, and Cultural Arts. Field number three (3) is closely related to efforts to improve the implementation and results of research conducted at the Faculty of Social Sciences UNJ. One of the study programs in FIS UNJ is the Pancasila and Citizenship Education Study Program (PPKN) (Ubaedillah, 2018; Buchholz, DeHart, & Moorman, 2020).

The research theme mandated by IKU and UNJ Research Development in the Field of Leading Research in 2021 – 2025 is directly related to the study that became the Research Umbrella in the PPKN Study Program. Umbrella This research has become Research Roadmaps which are divided into eight studies, namely (1) Civic Education Learning, (2) Political Education, (3) Legal Awareness, (4) Social Society, (5) Democracy and Human Rights, (6) Character Education and Local Wisdom, (7) Environment and Quality of Life, and (8) Global Citizenship. For this reason, this study seeks to develop the research umbrella of the PPKN FIS UNJ Study Program, in the fourth domain, namely Social Society, and the sixth domain, namely Character Education and Local Wisdom (Ubaedillah, 2018; Haldén, 2018).

By referring to the previous year's research, it was concluded that the traditional ceremony was obtained, that the Ngaruwat Bumi and Nyapu Overtime Ceremonies became a medium for transforming traditional values that were believed by the Banceuy Indigenous People as an effort to inculcate Pancasila values (Rahmadi, Hayati, & Nursyifa, 2020; Husen, et al., 2022; Casmana, et al., 2022). For this reason, it is interesting to examine whether the values of these customs are in accordance with the philosophical values of the nation, namely Pancasila. Therefore, this research study will discuss more deeply about what values and how to instill Pancasila values into early childhood through traditional ceremonies in Banceuy

Village, Subang, West Java (Rahmadi, Hayati, & Nursyifa, 2020; Haldén, 2018; Verger, Parcerisa, & Fontdevila, 2018).

In the journal *The International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities and Invention* the research of Sufni D. Ahmad (2018) concludes that to prevent fraud or irregularities by the leaders of an institution, then the values contained in Pancasila are perceived to be used as a code of ethics or the basis of leadership at all institutional levels, Meanwhile research conducted by Tedy Sudrajat (2018) on the Harmonization of regulation based on Pancasila Values through the Constitutional Court of Indonesia (Constitutional Review (Constitutional Review). vol 4.N0.2 December 2018), states that the development of the Pancasila paradigm regarding the rule of law must require the development of a democratic rule of law state, which juxtaposes the principle of the rule of law with the principle of harmony and complementarity with the sovereignty of the people. If the development of law is integrated into a more meaningful context, then the legal development characterized by Pancasila can be realized to resolve various community conflicts (Andreouli, & Brice, 2022; Hamer, & Finlayson, 2015; Weinberg, & Flinders, 2018).

Referring to the results of the research above, the difference in the research or state of the art research is, this research examines the inculcation of Pancasila values to early childhood through the Ngaruwat Bumi and Nyapu Overtime traditional ceremonies in the Banceuy Village, Subang, West Java.

The formulation of the problem in this research is (1) What are the Pancasila values that are instilled through the Ngaruwat Bumi and Nyapu Overtime Traditional Ceremonies in the Banceuy Indigenous People? (2) How is the inculcation of Pancasila values carried out through the Ngaruwat Bumi Traditional Ceremony and Nyapu Overtime in the Banceuy Indigenous People? (3) What is the model for inculcating Pancasila values to early childhood through the Ngaruwat Bumi Traditional Ceremony and Nyapu Overtime in the Banceuy Indigenous Community?

The purpose of this study was to find a model for inculcating Pancasila values through the Ngaruwat Bumi and Nyapu Overtime traditional ceremonies in the Banceuy Indigenous Community, Subang, West Java. Meanwhile, this research specifically aims to (1) obtain a model for the cultivation of Pancasila values through the Ngaruwat Bumi traditional ceremony and Nyapu Overtime. (2) Find out what Pancasila values are instilled through the Ngaruwat Bumi and Nyapu Overtime traditional ceremonies. (3) Obtain data on how to inculcate Pancasila values through the Ngaruwat Bumi and Nyapu Overtime ceremonies in the Banceuy Indigenous People.

The novelty of this research is the discovery of a model for inculcating Pancasila values to early childhood through the Ngaruwat Bumi Traditional Ceremony and Nyapu Overtime. This finding can be used as a reference to increase the actualization of Pancasila values in the Indonesian people and nation. In addition, the findings of This research can be used as a reference to maintain the existence of the values of Pancasila as the nation's culture in the midst of the penetration of foreign values which tend to be different and contradict the national identity.

Literature Review

The Strategic Plan of the State University of Jakarta (UNJ) designs and simultaneously develops Leading Research Fields for 2021 – 2025. Leading Research Fields for 2021 – 2025, number three (3) is Social Humanities, and Cultural Arts. Field number three (3) is closely related to efforts to improve the implementation and results of research conducted at the Faculty of Social Sciences UNJ. One of the study programs in FIS UNJ is the Pancasila and Citizenship Education Study Program (PPKN). This research encourages the realization of the basic research results of the faculty in the fields of Social Humanities and Cultural Arts through (a) Determination of scientific character based on the body of knowledge and the peculiarities of research objectives in study programs in the development of scientific traditions, (b)

Comparison of the characteristics of similar research with research institutions others, and (c) Conducting capacity building in research development (Weinberg, & Flinders, 2018; Peterson, & Bentley, 2017).

Similar research conducted previously, among others, was carried out by Sufni D. Ahmad (2018) In the journal *The International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities and Invention* (Vol 5 No. 9 (2018) Page No.: 4969-4973) the study concluded that to prevent the occurrence of fraud or irregularities by the leader of an institution, then the values contained in Pancasila are perceived to be used as a code of ethics or the foundation of leadership at all institutional levels. Research conducted by Via Nur Jannah with the title of *Instilling Pancasila Values, Especially the Value of Indonesian Unity in the Chinese Ethnic* (e-print.ums.ac.id. 2014). This study examines the association of Chinese people in Surakarta. The results showed that (1) the inculcation of Pancasila values, especially the value of Indonesian unity in the Surakarta Community Association, was carried out through training activities in cultural arts such as dance, wayang orang, gamelan, campursari and gymnastics, and (2) the value of Indonesian Unity was carried out through events. regular meetings such as seminars, social gathering, scholarships, and cheap medical treatment (Wiseman, Abdelfattah, & Almassaad, 2016; Wang 2021; Sarkadi, et al., 2022).

Instilling Pancasila Values in Shaping Children's Character as an Effort to Prevent "Lost Generation" at the NU Hidayatul Muttaqin Islamic Boarding School Education TPA, Pagutan (2019), by Sri Solehah. The results of this study state that (1) the implementation of the inculcation of Pancasila values in Islamic boarding schools is carried out by applying the pesantren curriculum as stated in the Minister of Religion Regulation No. 13 of 2014 concerning Islamic Religious Education as a reflection of the values of Pancasila which teaches moral education and habituation to students, (2) cooperation between pesantren managers, parents, and the relevant government in inculcating Pancasila values, and (3) imposing sanctions to students who violate the values of

Pancasila (Hamer, & Finlayson, 2015; Wang 2021; Patterson, & Choi, 2018).

Anzhar Ishal Afryand and Sapriya in *Untirta Civic Education Journal (UCEJ)* Vol. 3 No. 2 (2018), researching the Internalization of Pancasila Values through the Pancasila Study Center as an Effort to Strengthen the Nation's Ideology for the Young Generation at the Pancasila Study Center, Gadjah Mada University Yogyakarta, resulted in the findings that, (1) the system of internalizing Pancasila values as a true truth (Developing Pancasila as a living truth), the cultivation of Pancasila is one of the concrete manifestations of strengthening the Pancasila ideology, (2) the implementation of the internalization of Pancasila values can be categorized as an effort to strengthen national insight and Pancasila ideology in the midst of the emergence of radicalism movements, and considered capable of building understanding, skills, and behaviors that reflect the values of Pancasila in the life of the nation and state, and (3) the implications of implementing the internalization of Pancasila values are divided into three aspects, (a) knowledge and understanding of Pancasila values, (b) skills and attitudes or behavior, and (c) the combination of the two can raise awareness in implementing the values of Pancasila in society, nation and state (Buchholz, DeHart, & Moorman, 2020; Dalby, & Moussavi, 2016; Choi, Lawry, & Kim, 2019; Jørgensen, & Jørgensen, 2020).

International Journal for Educational Studies, 5 (1) (2012) illustrates the results of research conducted by Taniredja, Afandi, and Faridli with the title *The Appropriate Pancasila Education Contents to Implant Lofty Values for Indonesian Students*, namely (1) the foundation and aim of "Pancasila" Education; (2) "Pancasila" in the historical context of Indonesian struggle; (3) "Pancasila" as a philosophical system; (4) "Pancasila" as political ethic; (5) "Pancasila" as national ideology; (6) "Pancasila" in the state administration of the Indonesian Republic; and (7) "Pancasila" as social, national, and state living paradigm in Indonesia to be developed continuously in Indonesian community (Casma, et al., 2022;

Heikka, 2015; Bada, & Jita, 2022; Bada, & Jita, 2022).

Meanwhile Kurniawan, who researched on Pancasila as a Basis for the Nation's Character Education, resulted that Pancasila should be used as a guide for the Indonesian nation's life (Candan, & Başaran, 2023; Masud, 2020; Bergen, & Mollen, 2019; Baring, et al., 2021; Francis, et al., 2018). Furthermore, the nation's character education must be built based on Pancasila, no other sources such as Religion, Culture, and goal of National Education because Religion, Culture and goal of National education are part of Pancasila. (*Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research (ASSEHR)*, volume 125, (2017).

Methods

This study uses a qualitative approach. This study will describe the phenomena that occur, describe, and analyze how the model for inculcating Pancasila values occurred during the Ngaruwat Bumi and Nyapu Overtime traditional ceremonies in the Banceuy Subang Traditional Village. To complete this research, it is necessary to select informants from the traditional elders and traditional actors who are directly involved in the ceremony. The researcher will act as an instrument and play an active role in digging up data information in depth (in-depth interviews and probing questions). All data obtained and relevant will be analyzed as material for research wealth (Creswell, 2014).

Results and Discussions

The Banceuy Traditional Village has cool air all year round. This village is located at the foot of the Tangkuban Perahu mountains, West Java. The Banceuy Traditional Village is part of the Ciater District and the authority of the Subang Regency Government. The area of the Banceuy Traditional Village, according to the data is 157 hectares, which is divided into 47 hectares of forest, 78 hectares of rice fields, 20 hectares of plantation land, the remaining 12 hectares, inhabited by all Muslim residents, who live from

forest products, plantations, and rice fields as natural resources that are used as tourism objects.

The pattern of buildings in the Banceuy Indigenous village is neatly arranged as is where people live in general. Very different when compared to the Baduy people in Banten or Kampung Naga in Garut. This Banceuy Traditional Village does not have a typical building model, however, in every part of the house building there are rules that must be met, such as the location of the house, the door, a place to store rice or goah, and the position of the bedroom.

The sacred traditional ceremony for the Banceuy Indigenous people is Ruwatan Bumi or Ngaruwat Bumi. The word Ruwatan has the meaning of caring, which also means caring for and preventing residents from harm that can occur at any time (Rosyada, 2021). Whereas what is meant by earth is all customary land inhabited by the Banceuy people. Ruwatan Bumi aims to convey gratitude to God Almighty for everything that has been bestowed on the people of Banceuy in the form of earth products and all blessings. This ceremony is also a form of respect for the ancestors who have established this Banceuy Traditional Village. (Rosyada; 2021).

The planting of Pancasila values which is carried out in the implementation of the Ruwatan Bumi ceremony and related to early childhood, among others; (1) Cikibung; is an art of folk skills that is played during traditional ceremonies. Through this traditional art of Cikibung, the performers of traditional ceremonies present interesting games, among others, by rotating the sarong that is draped from the right shoulder to the left waist. Then as popular music is played, the kai sarong is spun in the air. Immediately, the Leader of the Event (at the time the research was conducted, the leader was the Traditional Elder) shouted "Lung ...", then immediately a sarong was thrown into the air. Participants who fail to throw into the air properly and beautifully, will be penalized in accordance with the orders of the Event Leader. This event is carried out only by adult traditional ceremony participants. From

the participants who were sanctioned, the values of local wisdom that were full of meaning were conveyed. The presentation can be done seriously or with a fresh joke, so that participants and audiences feel entertained as well as advised.

When compared with those of Sufni D. Ahmad (2018), Via Nur Jannah (2014), Sri Solehah (2019), Anzhar Ishal Afryand and Sapriya (2018), Taniredja, Afandi, and Faridli (2012), Kurniawan (2017), then the inculcation of Pancasila values in Banceuy is relatively different, namely conveying it by means of games played by parents, not by early childhood only. At least, this is done through the game Cikibung.

The inculcation of Pancasila values to early childhood is also carried out through Jibrut Art. Jibrut has been known to the Banceuy Indigenous People since the 1930s. This art form does not use equipment made of anything. Because the art of jibrut, uses the palms of the hands that are squeezed into the armpits of the players. After the palm is in the player's armpit, then it is moved in such a way that it produces a distinctive sound, such as a "preeet" sound. This activity lasts for a while, and in between games, the player gives advice, stories, or tales. It is from this oral story that the traditional values which are part of local wisdom are conveyed. Participants who heard the game felt entertained and at the same time received advice from the elders who played this jibrut.

In contrast to the results of research conducted by Sufni D. Ahmad (2018), Via Nur Jannah (2014), Sri Solehah (2019), Anzhar Ishal Afryand and Sapriya (2018), Taniredja, Afandi, and Faridli (2012), Kurniawan (2017), then the inculcation of Pancasila values to early childhood in Banceuy is carried out through the art of Jibrut. Through this art, early childhood is advised and given examples of good deeds, among the distinctive air sounds that come out of the fusion of the palms of the hands with the armpits.

Instilling Pancasila values into other early childhood is done through Miruha's scientific activities. Miruha is an activity of making sparks from dry bamboo. The model used is to use a small bamboo slat, then swipe it with a larger

sized bamboo slat. With a regular and fast friction frequency, then from friction the two bamboos will produce a burst of fire. In order to accommodate the focal point of the fire caused by the friction, tiwul or wood shavings or dry stems or dry leaves are flammable. This traditional fire-making activity was carried out by the ancestors of the Banceuy Traditional Village in order to make a fire stove in the saung they had built. Miruha is a simple activity but is proof of a scientific product of local values that need to be preserved. This form of activity also replaces the corrective function in modern times like today.

If the research conducted by Sufni D. Ahmad (2018), Via Nur Jannah (2014), Sri Solehah (2019), Anzhar Ishal Afryand and Sapriya (2018), Taniredja, Afandi, and Faridli (2012), Kurniawan (2017) oriented to the values of Pancasila which are formally conveyed in the classroom, the inculcation of Pancasila values to early childhood in the Banceuy Traditional Village is carried out by playing and outside the classroom. These Pancasila values are instilled in children through part of traditional ceremonies.

The instilling of Pancasila values in early childhood is also instilled through the kolecer game. Kolecer is a type of children's game that is also scientifically based. Koleceran is a game that utilizes wind power as an energy source to drive a spinning wheel for a kolecer (ie a fan made of bamboo or wood). Kolecer is made of bamboo or hardwood segments that are flat in shape, with varying sizes. The bamboo or wood segments are made in such a way that they form a propeller. The center is perforated to insert a small bamboo (barungbung) which is useful as a ring to connect the axle with a fan-shaped sheet of bamboo or wood. Its function is so that the kolecer can rotate perfectly. After the kolecer is finished, the child can use it to play. The way to play is to hold it in your hand, then carry it running while having fun. It can also be a large kolecer connected with long bamboo and placed on a house or tall tree or on a rice field bund, so that it can be enjoyed by many people. Even those who are more creative are given variations of paintings of wayang golek figures, such as dawala or semar. This kolecer rotation can

produce a melodious and consistent sound, so that it can entertain fans.

If the research conducted by Sufni D. Ahmad (2018), Via Nur Jannah (2014), Sri Solehah (2019), Anzhar Ishal Afryand and Sapriya (2018), Taniredja, Afandi, and Faridli (2012), Kurniawan (2017), examines the inculcation of Pancasila values through formal learning practiced by teachers and imitated by students, then at Banceuy, the instillation of Pancasila values to early childhood is carried out through traditional games. One way to do this is through a collector, as illustrated above. From this game, actually planting the values of Health, intelligence, and friendship with nature is taking place. These values are an inseparable part of the values of preserving the nation's culture as mandated in Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution.

Another finding from this research is the Nyapu Overtime activity which is part of the Ruwatan Bumi traditional ceremony. Nyapu Overtime is an activity to keep the environment clean from less commendable acts committed by people who are not responsible for environmental cleanliness. This activity has only been used in the last few years, in the traditional village of Banceuy. The Nyapu Overtime event is routinely held at the end of every month, by cleaning the village environment from garbage that is thrown carelessly by residents or visitors. Nyapu Overtime aims to protect the environment so that the Banceuy Traditional Village remains clean, beautiful, and sustainable.

Conclusion

Referring to the discussion above, this study can conclude that the values of Pancasila which are instilled in early childhood through the Ruwatan Bumi and Nyapu Overtime ceremonies are as follows.

The values of Pancasila that are instilled through the Ngaruwat Bumi Traditional Ceremony and Nyapu Overtime to early childhood in the Banceuy Indigenous community are Divine Values, Human Values, Unity Values, Deliberation and Representative Values, and Social Justice Values. The value planting activity

is carried out through a ceremony in the form of (a) Ritual Activities in the form of Hajat Mawar, Maulud Aki Leutik, Hajat Solokan, (b) Art Activities in the form of Rengkong, Tuunggulan, and Kolecer. While the cultivation of values through the Nyapu Overtime ceremony is Cleaning the Environment Together.

The values that exist in the community are instilled through the inclusion of the content of traditional messages that are directly related to the values of Pancasila. In the implementation of the Ngaruwat Bumi traditional ceremony, games of cikibung, jibrut, miruha, and kolecer are held in front of early childhood children, so that early childhood can follow the values instilled through these activities.

The custom or habit of Nyapu Overtime is carried out in an integrated manner with Ruwatan Bumi activities with the intention that the traditional village which is relatively full of garbage, because it was left by participants and visitors can be cleaned. The Nyapu Overtime activity is also carried out to maintain the cleanliness of the village, environment, and yard of the Banceuy Traditional Village residents.

The model of inculcating Pancasila values to early childhood through the Ngaruwat Bumi Traditional Ceremony and Nyapu Overtime in the Banceuy Indigenous Community is carried out persuasively through habituation and direct involvement of early childhood in traditional ceremonies, both as spectators and as actors. In this case, early childhood as perpetrators must obtain approval from parents and the willingness of the child himself.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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